

JCWS

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DIQQAT SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIR KO'RSATUVCHI
OMILLAR

Vol. 2 No. 7 (2024): Journal of Contemporary World Studies

<https://bestjournalup.com/index.php/jcws/>

SM
SOY MARINA

02.10.2024